

Investigation of tribological behavior of thin solid films

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Abstract. Tribology deals with friction and wear phenomena occurring between two surfaces in relative motion, directly affecting mechanical reliability, energy efficiency, and component lifetime. Particularly, as electronic devices continue to become smaller and more highly integrated, conventional lubrication methods face significant limitations. Consequently, research on surface modification based on thin solid films has been actively pursued to reduce surface friction and wear, thereby enhancing the durability of the system. To design such thin film coatings, it is essential to evaluate their mechanical and chemical properties using various precision instruments. Failure mechanisms must be analyzed through friction and wear experiments using a tribometer that induces relative motion such as reciprocating or rotational motion at the contact interface. Comprehensive analysis and understanding of coating failure mechanisms are recognized as key elements for more reliable device design. This study investigates the friction and wear behavior of thin solid films with various materials and thicknesses, with particular focus on the influence of the mechanical properties of coating materials on wear behavior. Wear evolution under different sliding configurations is compared, examining how brittle- and ductile-dominated deformation modes govern crack initiation, delamination, and materials removal. The findings provide mechanical insight into the relationship between coating mechanical properties and tribological behavior under repeated sliding contact.

Keywords: Friction, Wear, Failure mechanism, Thin solid film, Tribology.

1 Introduction

As electronic devices become smaller and incorporate more complex mechanical interfaces, frictional contact at micro-scale interfaces has emerged as a critical reliability challenge. Conventional liquid lubrication, though effective in traditional mechanical systems, is poorly suited to miniaturized electronic components due to spatial constraints, contamination concerns, and packaging limitations. Thin solid films have therefore emerged as a viable alternative, offering improved durability through targeted surface modification [1,2].

The design of thin film coatings requires comprehensive characterization of mechanical and chemical properties before tribological testing. Such characterization typically employs techniques including nanoindentation, atomic force microscopy (AFM), and Raman spectroscopy. Subsequently, tribological experiments are conducted through scratch, friction, and wear testing using a tribometer under reciprocating or rotational motion. After testing, failure mechanisms are identified using instruments such as confocal microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Understanding these failure modes is essential for developing durable coatings for systems under repeated contact. However, understanding the friction and wear behavior of thin solid films is challenging, as damage mechanisms are governed by the complex interaction of material composition, coating thickness, mechanical properties, and interfacial adhesion [3].

In this study, the friction and wear behaviors of thin film coatings with various materials and thicknesses are compared, identifying their failure characteristics during contact sliding. Furthermore, the relationship between mechanical properties on wear resistance is examined, along with current challenges in thin film coating design.

2 Experimental Method

To evaluate friction and wear behavior under sliding conditions, tribological experiments were conducted using various types of tribometers [4,5]. Reciprocating tribometers reproduced alternating sliding motion typical of micro-vibration in electronic devices and precision mechanical systems, characterized by bidirectional motion within a fixed stroke length. In contrast, pin-on-disk tribometers simulated continuous rotational sliding found in components such as bearings, seals, and rotating interfaces, where the contact point experiences sustained circular motion without directional reversal (see Fig. 1).

These complementary tribometer geometries enable precise control of normal load, sliding velocity, and contact pressure while permitting real-time measurement of tangential friction force throughout the sliding process. By systematically varying these parameters, the experiments capture the evolution of friction coefficients and identify critical transitions in wear mechanisms. Post-test wear track characterization using SEM, EDS and TEM reveal distinct damage morphologies depending on the experimental conditions. These tribological tests provide comprehensive insight into the failure mechanisms and wear progression of thin film coatings across diverse operating conditions, demonstrating how contact conditions influence the dominant wear phenomena.

Fig. 1. Schematic of tribometers (a) reciprocating type (b) pin-on cylinder type.

3 Discussion

The failure characteristics of thin solid films under sliding contact depend strongly on their deformation behavior — whether brittle or ductile [6]. Brittle coatings accommodate limited elastic strain before fracturing; once the critical stress threshold is exceeded, sharp crack initiation occurs, rapidly evolving into delamination, wear debris formation, or tearing. This may lead to friction force increase and accelerate material removal along the wear track. In contrast, ductile coatings develop progressive surface grooving and chipping. Although this prevents sudden failure, repeated contact can cause significant wear accumulation through material flow. The transition from elastic deformation to irreversible damage is also strongly influenced by loading mode, contact geometry, and cycling conditions, which govern stress accumulation within the coating and at the interface. This study shows that cycling sliding promotes fatigue-driven cracking in brittle films, whereas continuous sliding enhances shear-dominated wear in ductile films. These contrasting mechanisms demonstrate that wear resistance depends not only on hardness but on stress dissipation capability. Consequently, assessing coating wear resistance requires understanding its wear behavior under specific loading conditions, not merely its initial mechanical properties.

Friction and wear are complex phenomena resulting from the synergistic interaction of numerous factors, ranging from environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, to external parameters including normal load, sliding speed, and contact geometry. Also, the mechanical and chemical properties of thin solid films applied to the surface are important. To elucidate friction and wear mechanisms, researchers have developed tribometers that replicate actual operating environments and conducted systematic tribological experiments. Therefore, identifying the underlying wear mechanisms through well-designed tribological testing is essential for further reducing friction and wear and for guiding the development of more reliable thin film coatings. Through systematic investigation of thin film behavior during contact sliding, the major failure mechanism could be identified. The results are expected to aid in design of superior wear resistant thin film coatings for precision device applications.

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